

EURO-ARGO RISE WEB SITE

Ref.: D7.2_V1.0

Date: 07/05/2019

Euro-Argo Research Infrastructure Sustainability and Enhancement
Project (EA RISE Project) - 824131

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 824131.
Call INFRADEV-03-2018-2019 : Individual support to ESFRI
and other world-class research infrastructures

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Document Reference

Project	Euro-Argo RISE - 824131
Deliverable number	D7.2
Deliverable title	Euro-Argo RISE web site
Description	Project web site
Work Package number	WP7
Work Package title	Euro-Argo RISE visibility: communication and dissemination towards user's community
Lead Institute	E-A ERIC
Lead author	Estérine EVRARD
Contributors	Claire GOURCUFF
Submission date	07/05/2019
Due date	M03 –31 March 2019
Comments	The deliverable (web site) was set up in January. The delay in the report is mainly due to the implementation of the graphic charter and creation of templates.
Accepted by	Claire GOURCUFF

Document History

Version	Issue Date	Authors	Comments
1.0	07/05/2019	E. EVRARD	Initial version

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1 Introduction

1.1. General presentation

Within HORIZON 2020 Euro-Argo RISE project, a work package on communication and dissemination towards user's community (WP7) has been considered in order to enhance Euro-Argo visibility. The objectives of WP7 is both to propose fit for purpose services to Euro-Argo community and to attract new users as well as to enhance Euro-Argo visibility towards the general public.

This report contains the information regarding the creation of the Euro-Argo RISE project website.

It is the deliverable D7.2 identified in the description of work Annex 1 (Part A), in the WT2, page 10 of 50, which is due by the end of March 2019 (M03), M01 being January 2019.

1.2. Applicable documents

DA-1: Annex 1 to the grant agreement N°824131: "Description of work", date 20th November, 2018.

2 Web site

A web site was developed by the coordinator at the start of the project. The public URL of the project website is <https://www.euro-argo.eu/EU-Projects/Euro-Argo-RISE-2019-2022> and it has been online and visible for searching engines from January 2019.

The Euro-Argo RISE public web site was developed to act as an information hub about the project's aims, goals, activities and results.

Being updated regularly, the web site is integrated in the Euro-Argo ERIC web site to highlight that Euro-Argo RISE is a project that contributes to the development of the Euro-Argo Research Infrastructure.

The public section provides the following content:

- a) Overview of the project
- b) Partners: description of all consortium members taking part in the project
- c) Work packages: information about titles, leaders and objectives of all work packages
- d) Meetings: Description of events organized within the framework of the project
- e) News: any news published in this section will appear on Euro-Argo web site frontpage for a few months.
- f) Deliverables: This section allows partners and users to access the final documents (dissemination level: public).

Euro-Argo web site is the first online communication tool to present and disseminate the results and events throughout the project lifetime.

It will be updated by the E-A ERIC partner with material from all Euro-Argo RISE partners in order to present the latest news and will remain available after the end of the project.

Selection of Euro-Argo RISE website within Euro-Argo ERIC web site

Euro-Argo RISE web site structure